

**Why Lead?: Supporting Student Leadership in Placentia-Yorba Linda
Unified School District**

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Abstract

The purpose of this research project is to understand the trends of adolescents' leadership pursuit at their schools and in the local community. It is essential to cultivate young leaders so they can be well-rounded citizens of society and some of the most impactful leadership experiences occur within school leadership programs.

A case study was conducted on student leadership in Placentia-Yorba Linda Unified School District (PYLUSD), which serves around 24,000 students. PYLUSD has been recognized as a high-performing school district on a statewide and national level.

The purpose of this project was to research the overall impact of student leadership in PYLUSD and create a guide that will be free for all students to access. The guide will focus specifically on how to gain acceptance into application-based programs like Peer Leadership and ASB (Associated Student Body). The research will also provide rationale for how providing leadership opportunities to students relates to the district's core values and mission statement.

Qualitative data was collected for this research project. I interviewed two high school teachers and two middle school teachers. I also conducted interviews with four alumni: one is a college freshman and the other three are well established in their respective careers. This data was combined with information from scholarly articles and websites including the official PYLUSD website.

Introduction

When thinking about the topic of my senior project for the Cal State Fullerton Honors program, I knew I wanted to do something that would combine my passion for improving the lives of children in my local community, the education field and leadership. I was raised and currently reside in Yorba Linda, a town of about 60,000 people located in the hills of North Orange County, California. It is also home to the Placentia-Yorba Linda Unified School District (PYLUSD). PYLUSD is a school district that consists of about 24,000 students and 34 school sites in total. The district serves students from not only the cities of Yorba Linda and Placentia, but from the nearby cities of Anaheim, Fullerton and Brea. PYLUSD has been recognized as a top school district as 25 schools have been designated as California Distinguished Schools. 17 schools have been awarded the California Gold Ribbon and 8 schools have been given a Blue Ribbon, the nation's highest educational honor.

While a student in the PYLUSD, I was involved in various leadership programs such as Peer Leadership, Associated Student Body (ASB) and held various positions in clubs during high school. Now, as a student at Cal State Fullerton (CSUF), I have been a board member for on-campus organizations, a peer mentor, a teaching assistant and am currently serving as an executive officer in student government. From my experiences, I have grown tremendously, not

only as a leader, but as a person. I have learned integrity, responsibility, and adaptability, all of which are valuable skills that can be applied in my professional and personal life.

Reflecting on my previous and current leadership experiences, I realized the importance of providing leadership opportunities to middle school and high school students and supporting them in these roles. It is essential to cultivate future leaders so they can be well-rounded citizens of society. My goal for this project is to provide students with some insight into how they can make positive contributions to the world around them. Ultimately, I hope that this research, along with the companion student guide can inspire students to dedicate themselves to making their school and community a better place.

Why Focus On Student Leadership?

In recent years, there has been more focus on researching the impact of student leadership programs. According to Dempster and Lizzio (2007), there has been a steady decline of interest in civic engagement and community leadership among young people. The thought behind targeting studies specifically on student leadership is to address the issue of less workers committing to leadership roles in their careers. If young students are introduced to the idea of leadership, it is more likely they will have stronger leadership capabilities in the future. Through survey answers collected by Dempster and Lizzio, it was discovered that overall students want access to leadership opportunities and have more of an active role in overall school leadership.

Student leaders are encouraged to lead themselves before they lead others. This means that students begin to discover who they are and what they care about (Bowman, 2013). Students need to understand that being a leader is inspiring others to make a positive impact and that they have the power to advocate for issues they feel strongly about. For example, if a leadership class is hosting a supplies drive for a homeless shelter, students need to showcase that passion and it will inspire others to contribute. A student doesn't have to be in a leadership class to be considered a leader as every student has a voice. A leader's goal is to not lead for themselves, but to lead for others. Leaders should strive to make change not because of praise, but because they want to make a difference and achieve a greater goal. Students need to trust in their leadership abilities, acquire the ability to empathize with others and have compassion in order to effectively lead (Bowman, 2013).

Methodology

As part of my research, I collected qualitative data by conducting interviews on Zoom with four activities directors and four PYLUSD Leadership alumni. All of the participants were recruited through email or personally asked by the researcher. Out of the four activities directors, two were high school teachers (male and female) and two were middle school teachers (male and female). All of the activities directors are credentialed teachers who have experience teaching academic subjects, but also are responsible for overseeing school leadership programs like ASB

and Peer Leadership. Activities directors help assist student leaders in the planning and implementation of school functions and activities. Out of the alumni participants, three are well established in their respective careers and one is a current college student. Alumni careers consist of a firefighter/paramedic, a director of an independent living service who is also the founder of a nonprofit organization that raises awareness of childhood cancer, an IT specialist at a credit union and a college student.

Findings

Through conducting my interviews with activities directors and alumni, I identified five major themes that define student leadership in PYLUSD. First, is diversity and inclusion. Activities directors and alumni acknowledge that it is important for a leadership class to reflect the student population of a school. Student leaders are chosen to be voices in decision making involving school events and activities, which requires input from students of all different academic and personal backgrounds. One activities director stated, “I need to make sure to include special education students, students who are English language learners, McKinney-Vento students who are considered homeless, GATE and Honors students. I have students from every group on campus because if we are the ones who are supposed to be making decisions on how to spend money, how to put on a dance. If we are the ones that are supposed to be making those kinds of decisions for the other 700 kids in our school, I need to have voices from everyone.” Every student has the potential to be a leader and to develop leadership skills, as one activities director said, “I really truly believe that leaders come in all shapes and sizes. I believe that anyone can be a leader. I think specifically what I look for is for someone’s heart to be in it. I want someone’s passion for school, passion for ASB or passion for leadership to come through.” Another activities director also went on to say that he has seen certain populations of students, such as at-risk students benefit immensely from their involvement in leadership, “I’ve had students as a 7th grader who wanted to be in ASB in 8th grade and even though they made some bad choices, I put them in leadership because they were more at risk. A kid who’s 4.0 may not need the same skills as the kid who is at-risk. They’re going to have a successful year, but also develop some leadership skills and develop a purpose. You are making them feel a part of something. I’ve seen GATE students become really close friends with an at-risk student and I think it’s beautiful.”

Second, is serving over self. Activities directors are trying to instill in their students a desire to give back to their school and community through purposeful service. According to Bowman (2013), students should live by the belief that “to serve is to live” which means that the desire to serve should be natural and come before developing into a leader. Serving leaders are connected to members of their local and school community because of their desire to give back. Leaders listen to the needs and wants of the student population and try to accommodate them in the best way they can. One activities director said that he is constantly reminding his students to not think about what they personally want in an activity or an event, but what other students

would want to see, “I’ve always taught my students to think of what is the purpose of what we are doing. What is the point of an assembly, what is the point of a hot chocolate bar? I think it’s important for them to have those discussions. Like are we doing it just to do it, because I don’t want extra work, I want to be doing something because it has meaning. You’re teaching them critical thinking and “the why?” Why are you doing something. It’s teaching them to be purposeful, to have intentionality with every action. Our hot chocolate bar for the teachers took almost 10-15 hours to plan to make those teachers feel good for 15 minutes, but there was purpose in it. I tell them there has to be purpose.” Student leaders also have the opportunity to incorporate their personal interests in their service. An alumni student said, “I was able to put on an event called School Rocks! Day. So basically what we did was we got 100 rocks, paint and paintbrushes and set up tables. Every student who came to our table was able to paint a rock. They could keep it if they wanted to, but the main thing was that we were going to take these rocks and donate them to the hospital for a child to have. People painted smiley faces, encouraging words or just fun pictures. This is just to show that our students care about them and they’re not alone. This is something that is really close to my heart and I got to bring that part of me to school which I thought was so special.”

In addition, there is an emphasis on cultivating school spirit in student leadership. One activities director states that a part of school leadership is, “keeping school culture alive through our activities and events. My role [as activities director] is to instill in my leaders, my students, the idea that we are serving our school community. I try to tell the kids that we are running these events to get our student population involved. It can be as small as a spirit day or it can be as big as an assembly or a dance.” The major goal of a school leadership program is to create a positive school environment where every student feels welcomed. Connecting students to their school makes them want to attend everyday and participate in events. Activities directors emphasize student leaders have a strong intrinsic motivation to spread school spirit. One activities director says, “It’s not difficult to get students who are already spirited and deeply care about the school to participate because individually they are motivated and want to be here. I think most of the kids in leadership also have very supportive families. They know that our school is a safe place to be, so if they aren’t home, they might stay after school until 4:30pm. They are intrinsically motivated to do what it takes to support the school. It might not be being in the front line of the student section at a game yelling and screaming, but right now they are behind the scenes. Leading by example is really important and as an advisor I think I have been able to do that. I like to be there with my students and illustrate to them what it means to be a part of stuff.” Another activities director emphasizes the fact that student leaders not only need to have intrinsic motivation to serve, but have to incorporate input from the student body in order to engage them in school. She says, “I feel like every year, the students want to make this year better than the last. I think they find the motivation within themselves, but we also talk about things like serve over self as we want to make sure we put others before ourselves. Everyone has something that they are passionate about and I use those passions to drive their wants and their

motivation to be passionate about other people's things. If you want people to be passionate about your thing, you have to give passion to other people's things as well."

The fifth theme is that being involved in leadership provides students with the opportunity for self-discovery. One alumna describes how she was not aware of her leadership potential until the school activities director approached her, "What made me what to pursue leadership was the teacher saying you have what it takes. I still had to try out or campaign, but he noticed that I had what it takes to be a leader. I thought I'm just being me, I'm just being my energetic self and when somebody noticed that it was like, "Oh, that might be fun, ok let me try that!" It's all about the school system and getting the school united and that felt right down my alley. I look back on high school as some of the best years of my life so far. I loved every minute of it and when I had kids, I wanted to make sure that they could appreciate it and take everything for when it came and enjoy every minute of it and do as much as you can and be involved because that's how you make new friends, make connections and you also build your character. I feel that who I was then has carried on who I am now. I apply the passion that I had for getting the school united in spirit to my careers with how I look at things. Having that passion, finding that passion, finding the why behind what you are doing and enjoying it." Many students such as this alumni, may not have awareness of the qualities they possess until someone like an educator recognizes and encourages them. Students may also not be aware of certain passions until they are given the space to explore and leadership programs can be one opportunity for students to pursue different interests. One activities director says that she makes a priority to incorporate assignments in her class that contribute to a student's self discovery, "I am passionate about developing the inner leader, so I require a lot of leadership lessons. I always say to my kids you can't be a good leader for others until you are a good leader for yourself. So we develop the self before we can go and lead others." Leadership allows the students to think about their values, what they are passionate about and how they would approach different situations. The same activities director goes on to describe two special projects she does in her class. "Every year, I do a quote project and the students have to find a quote that resonates with them and they really have to dissect the meaning of it and state how it relates to their lives. It's a project about learning about themselves. So many times the kids chose quotes that have meanings for them. Then they provide or create a board with that quote and present to the class about it. I also like to do this project where they have to find a leadership inspiration. They need to find a leader in history, it doesn't have to be a famous leader, but they have to pick one, research them and present it to the class. Like why were their leadership skills and abilities important."

Discussion

The presence of school leadership programs in PYLUSD align with the district's mission statement, core values and vision. By being a part of a leadership program, students have the chance to participate in an experience that will, "empower them to become responsible, ethical and contributing citizens." Leadership also promotes students to develop integrity, to practice

collaboration with others, to pursue innovative ideas and strive for overall excellence. Leadership programs help to promote a positive learning environment for all students and will help them to gain skills that will be applicable to college or a career. As this research is specifically centered on middle school and high school students, it is important to connect leadership skills with college and career readiness. Some competencies that employers value most are oral/written communication skills, teamwork, ethical-decision making, critical thinking skills and ability to apply knowledge to real world situations (Peck, 2018). Alumni and activities directors referenced each of these in their responses as skills that they have learned by participating in leadership. Particularly the alumni have gone all to obtain careers or are pursuing higher education and have applied leadership principles to their lives in some way.

Effective, transformative leadership programs give students the opportunity to develop the skills that will help students reach their academic and personal goals (Peck, 2018). One alumni said, “I helped out planning a Winter Formal, a Homecoming and I also was given a project to order merchandise for football games. When you plan for these events you are now a 17 or 18 year old calling a hotel for an event, reserving banquet rooms, having to reserve a photographer, you’re having to figure out what the cost is, and what you’re going to serve, just the whole of things. So real life skills you can apply to aspects of your life after school. Like for the merchandise for football games, I had to decide how many pieces I wanted, if we go with this many it’s going to cost this much, how much are we going to charge and what is the profit margin going to be. When dealing with Homecoming, I had to call a props company in Fullerton and rent a backdrop. I needed to make sure we had a deposit on it and how are we going to pay for it. I was also responsible for packing it up and getting it back to them in a timely manner. So those types of projects force you to learn how to deal with issues in the real world.” Supporting student leadership in PYLUSD is crucial because it allows students to gain these types of experiences and I hope this research and the accompanying guide will encourage students to become more involved with school and local community service.

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